

Some Ligational Aspects of Tartrazine. Stabilities and c.f.s.e. of Its Binary Complexes with Some Bivalent Metal Ions

S. N. LIMAYE and M. C. SAXENA*

Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 003

Manuscript received 13 March 1984, revised 16 July 1984, accepted 19 January 1985

Practical proton-ligand stability constant of tartrazine (trzne) and metal-ligand stability constants of its 1:1 binary complexes with some bivalent metal ions, *viz.*, UO_2^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Be^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} have been determined *pH*-metrically using Irving-Rossotti titration technique at 25° and ionic strength of 0.2 (mol dm^{-3} NaClO_4). The $\log K_{ML}^M$ values have been used to evaluate the 10Dq and c.f.s.e. for the complexes. The general order of stability with respect to metal ions has been found to be, $\text{VO}^{2+} > \text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Be}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} < \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+}$.

TARTRAZINE¹ (trzne; trisodium salt of 3-carboxy-5-oxo-1-(*p*-sulphophenyl)-4-[(*p*-sulphophenyl)azo]pyrazole) is a basic azo dye (CI. 19140, acid yellow-23) used for dyeing foodstuffs and also as a preservative. It has been used in amperometric titrations² as a redox indicator^{3,4}, and as sodium salt in inks. Its binary and ternary EDTA complexes with the lighter lanthanide metal ions in solution have been reported earlier by us⁵.

The present work deals with the determination of stability constants ($\log K_{ML}^M$) of its binary complexes with some bivalent metal ions, *viz.*, UO_2^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Be^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} using Irving-Rossotti *pH* titration technique⁶. The $\log K_{ML}^M$ values have been used to evaluate the 10Dq and c.f.s.e. values for the complexes with 3d metal ions.

Experimental

Standard solutions of metal ions were prepared by dissolving the nitrates, chlorides, or sulphates in double-distilled water. The dye supplied by I.C.I. (India), was further purified by recrystallisation. The usual titration sets were prepared keeping the metal-ligand ratio at 1:5. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 (mol dm^{-3} NaClO_4). The sets were titrated against 0.2 mol dm^{-3} carbonate-free sodium hydroxide and the *pH* was recorded on an Elico LI-120 digital type *pH* meter.

Results and Discussion

The calculated values of practical proton-ligand stability constant of the ligand ($\log K_1^H$) and the metal-ligand stability constant ($\log K_{ML}^M$) of the 1:1 binary complexes along with their ΔG values have been recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANT OF LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 1:1 BINARY COMPLEXES

	I = 0.2 mol dm^{-3} NaClO_4 , Temp. = 25°				
	H^+	UO_2^{2+}	VO^{2+}	Mn^{2+}	Co^{2+}
$\log K_{ML}^M$	10.45	9.58	10.00	5.55	5.95
$-\Delta G$ kcal mol^{-1}	—	13.15	13.72	7.61	8.17
	Ni^{2+}	Cu^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Be^{2+}	Cd^{2+}
$\log K_{ML}^M$	6.65	7.80	6.85	9.05	4.05
$-\Delta G$ kcal mol^{-1}	9.72	10.92	8.17	12.41	5.56

The proton-ligand stability constant has been calculated from the $\bar{n}H$ values lying in the range $0 < \bar{n}H < 1$. From the *pH* titration plots (not shown) it is evident that ligand (Tartrazine-I) liberates only

one proton at higher *pH* region. This may be due to deprotonation of the carboxylic group of the pyrazole ring.

The bivalent metal ion may combine with the ligand liberating the carboxylate proton in the lower *pH* region. Although a certain amount of ambiguity seems to be involved in the structure of the metallic complexes of tartrazine, it appears that the ligand behaves as bidentate and forms a six-membered chelate ring through the carboxylate and azo nitrogen.

The metal-ligand formation constants have been determined from the $\bar{n}$ values lying in the range $0 < \bar{n} < 1$. Only 1:1 complexes have been studied in view of the fact that precipitation occurs at

relatively higher pH values (~ 6.8 for Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} , and a little less than 5.0 for UO_2^{2+} , VO^{2+} and Be^{2+}). The plots of $\bar{n}/[L]$ vs $[L]$ have been found to be smooth indicating the absence of any polynuclear species.

The log K_{ML}^M values have been found to lie in the order $\text{VO}^{2+} > \text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Be}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} < \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+}$. Amongst the 3d elements, Cu^{2+} with d^9 configuration forms the most stable complex which may be due to Jahn-Teller effect.

Table 2 records the calculated values⁷ of c.f.s.e. and 10Dq for the complexes with the 3d metal ions. The 10Dq values lie in the range 8000-15000 cm^{-1} and agree well with the general order of magnitude

of 10Dq for the hydrates and other complexes of 3d bivalent cations⁸. The literature values⁹ of log K_{ML}^M for the complexes of these metal ions with ammonia, pyridine, acetic acid, ethylenediamine and oxalic acid have been used to evaluate the c.f.s.e. and 10Dq values. These are presented in Table 2. These values indicate that tartrazine can be used as a ligand of comparable strength. Its coordination sites, however, involve some ambiguity.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. Y. G. Kher, Head, Department of Chemistry for providing facilities and to I. C. I. (India) for supplying the dye sample gratis. One of the authors (M.C.S.) is thankful to M. P. Council of Science and Technology for a research grant.

TABLE 2—EVALUATION OF C.F.S.E. AND 10Dq FROM STABILITY CONSTANTS

	Mn ²⁺	Fe ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Zn ²⁺
Tartrazine						
C.F.S.E.	0	—	24.4	44.2	37.8	0
10 Dq	0	—	8540	15470	13230	0
Pyridine						
C.F.S.E.	0	44.5	41.5	30.4	45.7	0
10 Dq	0	15575	14525	10640	15955	0
Acetic acid						
C.F.S.E.	0	—	—	27.3	42.6	0
10 Dq	0	—	—	9555	13910	0
Ammonia						
C.F.S.E.	0	42.5	42.0	29.3	47.3	0
10 Dq	0	14875	14700	10255	16250	0
Ethylenediamine						
C.F.S.E.	0	45	45.7	32	55	0
10 Dq	0	15750	15995	11300	19250	0
Oxalic acid						
C.F.S.E.	0	44.0	41.5	29.2	45.2	0
10 Dq	0	15400	14525	10220	15866	0

References

1. JU. LURIE, "Handbook of Analytical Chemistry", MIR Publishers, Moscow, 1975, p. 219.
2. G. POPA, D. NERGOIU and G. BAIULESCU, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1960, **22**, 200.
3. R. BELCHER, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1950, **4**, 468.
4. M. H. HASHMI and A. A. AYAZ, *Analyst*, 1964, **89**, 147.
5. S. N. LIMAYE and M. O. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 698.
6. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
7. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Wiley-Eastern Ltd., New Delhi, 1976, p. 94.
8. D. NICHOLLS, "Complexes and First Row Elements", Macmillan, London, 1974, p. 64.
9. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VASIL'EV, "Instability Constants of Complex Compounds", D. Van Nostrand, New York, 1966, Appendix.